

Factors of Investment Decision Practices among Certified Public Accountants in Davao del Norte

JOE MARI N. FLORES, CPA, MSA¹, VICENTE SALVADOR E. MONTAÑO, DBA²

¹Assistant Professor of Department of Accounting Education at UM Tagum College,

²Dean of College of Business Administration at University of Mindanao, Davao City

Abstract: The objective of this study is to identify the determinant factors of investment decision practices and further, to develop a framework that characterizes the investment decision practices among certified public accountants in Davao Del Norte. This research is significant for investors to enhance their capacity to decide on investments and provide investment managers better ways of designing their products and services. The informants of this study were 150 CPAs using a researcher's modified questionnaire that was personally administered. The data were analyzed using Data Reduction Analysis, Kaiser Meyer-Olkin measure of sampling adequacy and Barlett's test of sphericity and Factor Rotation Method. Using the exploratory factor analysis, the study reveals that Economic Expectation, Herding Effect, Market Information, Third Party Opinion, Financial Information, News and Government Influence, Firm Perception, Over-confidence and Firm Image best influences the investment decision practices of CPAs in Davao del Norte.

Keywords: *accountancy, certified public accountants, exploratory factor analysis, investment decisions, Philippines*

I. INTRODUCTION

Investments are made with the hope of a good return in the future. It appears to be appealing to a significant number of people because it helps them to engage in decision-making by investment. Investors can exercise decision-making and, therefore, can reassess their ability to make accurate choices by analyzing these results. However, this investment decision-making is a difficult task for investors, mainly because of the different biases that can cause people to emphasize or discount information or the refusal to acknowledge an opportunity. Although many have recognized that investment decisions can be made by individuals and different commercial enterprises, using a broad variety of opportunities for use and investment. However, in many cases, different variables, such as beliefs, previous experiences and feelings, have an impact on investment decisions, and individuals act in an unforeseen, irrational and irresponsible behavior resulting from long-term bad returns (Gill et al., 2018; Mahalakshmi and Anuradha, 2018)

A well-informed investor is a well-secured investor. Before making investment decisions, investors must empower themselves through information. Many investors could have avoided troubles and losses had they have well-grounded investment decisions. Thus, Investors ought to be vigilant and up to date to acquire favored desires (Farooq, 2015). Well-informed investment decisions facilitate certified public accountants and other investors to reduce mistakes and inaccuracy in making decisions brought by personal, company practices and other factors and biases. Moreover, an enhanced consideration of different factors and decreased illogicality of investors will lessen instability in the market. Government and other agencies can use the results of the study to set up strategies and investment guidelines. They can educate investors and even equity fund managers of establishments to recognize their errors based upon these factors (Qureshi and Hunjra, 2012).

Rational Expectation Theory, developed by economist Robert Lucas in the 1970s from the United States, opines that investors make investment choices that are backed-up by their logical perspectives, the experiences they have, and the data at hand. Some critical literature works also show congruence and state that investors are expected to react realistically when chasing their benefits. They are always assumed to be rational creatures. Investors' consider the

market condition before investing that hard-earned money by placing different techniques such as capital asset pricing model and other technical and fundamental investment approaches. (Islamoglu, Apan and Ayvali, 2017).

In the above context, the researcher decided to conduct the study of the investment decision practices among the certified public accountants in Davao del Norte. There are existing studies such as mentioned above; however, those studies have focused on some other professionals, unlike Certified Public Accountants who have fundamental knowledge about investments, therefore more reliable to refer to. The researcher has also chosen to conduct the study in Davao del Norte since it was once the haven of different investment activities in the region. Moreover, the investment decision process study has always been of prime interest to financial and banking, economics, administration, and other studies. Therefore, the conduct of this study contributes to their existing literature gap, especially in the local setting, particularly in Davao del Norte.

II. METHOD

Presented are the research steps and procedures that were taken by the researcher in this study. These include the Participants, Research Instruments, Design, and Procedure. Simple random sampling was used wherein 150 certified public accountants participated as respondents.

The primary tool used in the data gathering process was the researcher's constructed instruments taken from various literature and sources modified to fit the study and were subjected to the experts' validation. In addition, the reliability of the questionnaires was tested through pilot testing using Cronbach Alpha (Gliem, 2003).

The quantitative, non-experimental design of research using exploratory factor analysis (EFA) technique was employed in this study. Exploratory factor analysis technique is a non-experimental design and the best design to effectively extract information from large bodies of interrelated data, where the researcher summarizes the data by grouping correlated variables in a natural setting without manipulation or control. The quantitative, non-experimental design of research using exploratory factor analysis (EFA) technique was employed in this study. Exploratory factor analysis technique is a non-experimental design and the best design to effectively extract information from large bodies of interrelated data, where the researcher summarizes the data by grouping correlated variables in a natural setting without manipulation or control (Hair and et al.).

The proponent submitted the pertinent documents to the UM Ethics Review Committee (UMERC) for the approval of conducting the survey. Then, the researcher sent a letter of permission to conduct the study, signed by the adviser and endorsed by the Dean of the Professional Schools, to the President of PICPA - Davao del Norte. Before distributing the questionnaires, the researcher explained to the respondents the rationale of the study for them to understand its importance. Survey questionnaires were administered and handed personally by the researcher to the identified respondents from different sectors (Academe, Public, Government, and Private Industry). IT was done to ensure 100% retrieval of the questionnaire and provide an immediate response to any possible inquiries.

Subsequently, questionnaires were retrieved and checked for any missing entries. They were collected immediately after being filled out. The survey was conducted for two weeks commencing the second week until the last week of February of 2020. After retrieval, the responses were tabulated and processed using appropriate statistical tools. Exploratory factor analysis enabled the researcher to determine the number of components of investment, making decision behavior. Item loadings were determined, and items with similar themes were grouped with appropriate component names. Items that did not reach the cut-off point or have double-loadings were eliminated. Finally, the results were then for the study's purpose.

The statistical tool utilized in the research were hierarchical clustering ward method, KMO and Bartlett's test and factor rotation method. In this study hierarchical clustering ward method was used to reduce significant items or elements into a meaningful group or clusters based on similarities without any pre-classified grouping before proceeding to exploratory factor analysis, the KMO and Bartlett's test was used to determine the index of the factors of audit quality financial statements and to extract the constructs of investment decision practices, and factor rotation model to minimize the complexity of the factor loadings to make the structure simpler to interpret. Exploratory factor analysis was carried out to identify the factors of investment decision practices.

III. RESULTS

The Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin (KMO) Index is used for measuring the sampling adequacy (Kaiser and Rice, 1974). It's often used as a comparison index to see whether the magnitudes of the observed relationship coefficients and partial correlation coefficients are likely to unify on components. This metric ranges from 0 to at least one; a value of 0.6 is suggested as a minimum for a factor to begin, but values closer to 1 are preferred. In Table 1, the test results for KMO

index are 0.765, 0.727 and 0.784 for clusters 1-2, 1-2 and 2 respectively. Since the test size exceeded the appropriate value of 0.6, the result implied that the test was sufficient and worthwhile. This research demonstrates that the data can be grouped into smaller sets of underlying factors and that exploratory factor analysis can be used properly.

Moreover, analysis also included the Bartlett’s test of sphericity. In this study, table 1 shows that the test value for cluster 1-1 (603), degree of freedom (df) of 45, $p < 0.05$; cluster 1-2 (732.66), degree of freedom (df) of 78, $p < 0.05$; test value of (603), degree of freedom (df) of 45, $p < 0.05$ for cluster 2. Therefore, the dataset per cluster is believed to be suitable for factor analysis (Stewart, 1981). The significance-value of Bartlett’s test of sphericity should be lesser than 0.05 in order to be small-enough to reject the hypothesis Armstrong and Soelberg, (1968). The data has undergone principal component analysis (PCA) to identify the determinant structures. Principal component analysis (PCA) is used to find out whether certain items measure common factors (Henson and Roberts, 2006).

Table 1
KMO and Bartlett’s Test Result

Test	Value		
	Cluster 1-1	Cluster 1-2	Cluster 2
Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin Measure of Sampling Adequacy.	0.765	0.727	0.784
Bartlett’s Test of Sphericity	Approx. Chi-Square	603	732.66
	Degree of Freedom	45	78
	Significance	$p < 0.05$	$p < 0.05$
			$p < 0.05$

The standard result of exploratory factor analysis can be identified using the latent roots criterion through getting the total value of the variances explained. The total variance explained shows the result by identifying the value of the eigenvalues of the factors and the variance of each factor. As seen in table 2, 3 and 4, an aggregate of 27 of the items (9 items for cluster 1-1, 12 items for cluster 1-2 and 6 items for cluster 2) successfully loaded out of the 100 items subjected in the extraction procedure. Also, results revealed that an aggregate of nine factors or components can be extracted from the 100 items considered for dimensional reduction. These nine factors explained 67.287, 66.866 and 65.358 percent cumulative variations in the data for all clusters 1-1, 1-2 and 2 respectively.

Presented in table 2 are the degrees of variance explained by the explored dimensions or components of investment making decision behavior for cluster 1-1. Component 1 has a sum of squared loading value of 3.912 and explains 39.116 percent of the variance of investment making decision behavior. Component 2 has a sum of squared loading value of 1.674 and explains 16.743 percent of the variance of investment making decision behavior. Lastly, component 3 has a sum of squared loading value of 1.143 and explains 11.428 percent of the variance of investment making decision behavior. Overall, the three dimensions of investment making decision behavior explain 67.287 percent of the variance for the cluster.

Also presented in table 3 are the degrees of variance explained by the explored dimensions or components of investment making decision behavior for cluster 1-2. Component 1 has a sum of squared loading value of 4.09 and explains 31.462 percent of the variance of investment making decision behavior. Component 2 has a sum of squared loading value of 2.062 and explains 15.862 percent of the variance of investment making decision behavior. Component 3 has a sum of squared loading value of 1.35 and explains 10.385 percent of the variance of investment making decision behavior. Lastly, Component 4 has a sum of squared loading value of 1.19 and explains 9.157 percent of the variance of investment making decision behavior. Overall, the four dimensions of investment making decision behavior explain 66.866 percent of the variance for cluster 1-2.

More so, presented in table 4 are the degrees of variance explained by the explored dimensions or components of investment making decision behavior for cluster 2. Component 1 has a sum of squared loading value of 2.833 and explains 47.219 percent of the variance of investment making decision behavior. Component 2 has a sum of squared loading value of 1.088 and explains 18.139 percent of the variance of investment making decision behavior. Overall, the four dimensions of investment making decision behavior explain 65.358 percent of the variance for cluster 2.

Table 2
Total Variance Explained- Cluster 1-1

Component	Rotation Sums of Squared Loadings		
	Total	% of Variance	Cumulative %
1	3.912	39.116	39.116
2	1.674	16.743	55.859
3	1.143	11.428	67.287

Table 3
Total Variance Explained- Cluster 1-2

Component	Rotation Sums of Squared Loadings		
	Total	% of Variance	Cumulative %
1	4.09	31.462	31.462
2	2.062	15.862	47.324
3	1.35	10.385	57.709
4	1.19	9.157	66.866

Table 4
Total Variance Explained- Cluster 2

Component	Rotation Sums of Squared Loadings		
	Total	% of Variance	Cumulative %
1	11.832	24.650	24.650
2	10.332	21.524	46.174

An orthogonal rotation (VARIMAX) technique was used since it has the ability to produce a better construction in terms of the content legitimacy of the identified factors. In this study, the cut-off point of ± 0.50 for the coefficient was used for the 100-item scale. Setting a cut-off point above the minimum threshold results in an improved factor structure and assisted in formulating the factor rotation. The factors of investment making decision practices of certified public accountants in Davao del Norte are identified based on the item loadings. Based on the rotated component matrix, there are 9 components in total for cluster 1-1, 1-2 and 2 which was generated using principal component analysis, as presented in table 6

Table 7 illustrates the loadings of the items that comprise component of investment making decision practices from clusters 1-1, 1-2 and 2 namely, Economic Expectation, Herding Effect, Market Information, Third Party Opinion, Accounting Information, Firm Ethics, Environmental Factor, Overconfidence and Firm Image.

There are 3 items that were found out to comprise the first factor. These attributes speak of an investment behavior that is influenced by the stock volume, stock types and expected prices. Consequently, this factor is named "Economic Expectation" factor. Likewise, factor loadings of the second component or factor of investment making decision practices include items that speak of an investment behavior that perceives analysis other investors' as important in buying and selling equities. It also considers the reactions of other investors before investing and considers the stock marketability of firm before investing. Thus, this factor is named "Herding Effect". Also, same table shows the factor loadings that comprise the third factor of investment decision behavior. These items speak of a practice which assures stock investment is safe, considers the situation the economy before making a decision to invest and searches for information from different financial entities to help in deriving investment decisions. In consequence, this factor is named "Market Information".

The same table illustrates the loadings of the items that comprise the factors of investment making decision behavior from cluster 1-2 where 4 factors were present that constitutes the fourth to seventh factors. There were Four items found out to comprise the fourth factor. This factor speaks of a behavior that considers friend, co-worker or a family member's opinions in making investment decisions. As a result, this factor is named "Third Party Opinion". More so, factor loadings of the fifth factor of investment decision practices include three items. These items speak of a behavior that relies on previous information in the market for next investments and considers to forecasts the prices of stock 48behavior48ts in the future and the accounting data of the entity. So, this dimension is named "Financial

Information". Likewise, factor loadings of the sixth factor of investment making decision practices only include two items. These attributes speak of a behavior which perceives news, media and political instability largely influence in making investment decisions. Thus, this dimension is named "News and Government Influence". Lastly, the same table reveals the loadings of items which comprise seventh factor of investment making decision behavior in this cluster. There are also two items that were found out to comprise this factor. This item perceives firms' ethics and it's participation in community development are essential in deciding for an investment. Therefore, this dimension is named "Firm Ethics".

Shown also in table 7 the factor loadings of the items that comprise the component or factor of investment making decision behavior from cluster 2 where there 2 factors or dimensions were present and constitutes the eighth and ninth factors of investment decisions. There 4 items that were found out to comprise the eighth factor. These attributes speak of a behavior that considers confidence and complete knowledge of stock markets in investment decisions. It also speaks to dispose stock investments when it guaranties immediate gain realization. Consequently, this dimension is named "Overconfidence" factor. Similarly, factor loadings of the ninth factor of investment making decision behavior in this cluster include only two items. These attributes speak of a behavior that considers investment based on affection for an entities offered goods and services and is also affected by the statements from government officials in making investments. As a result, this dimension is named "Firm Image".

Table 6
Rotated Component Matrix

Item Number	1-1			1-2				2	
	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9
44. The quantity of stock from other investors affects my investment making decisions.	.838								
45. The expected prices and the types of stocks from other investors affect my investment making decisions.	.894								
46. The buying and selling behavior of other investor affects my investment making decisions.	.867								
68. The analysis of other investors is important in buying and selling equities.		.729							
75. I consider the reactions of other investors in making my investments		.770							
76. I consider the stock marketability of firm before investing.		.724							
10. The highest safety considerations in my stock investments are assured in making investment options.						.701			
12. The future condition in the economy is considered in making investment options.						.804			
13. The information from different outlet such as brochures and magazines of financial entities help me in making investment options.						.796			

32. Family member's opinions in investment decisions matter in making investment options.	.737	
33. My friend or co-worker recommendations help me in investments.	.791	
79. I like to invest on stocks which are well recommended by family members.	.812	
80. Friend recommendations matters on my investment decisions.	.770	
49. History in the market experiences affects my investment decisions.	.743	
50. Forecasting of share prices and the accounting performance is considered in making investment options.	.788	
51. The recent rate of returns of my investment impacts my investment activities.	.819	
52. I make sure that the rate of return is equal to or higher than the average returns before making investment options.	.661	
89. Perceived ethics of the firm affects my decision to invest.	.872	
90. Involvement in the enhancement of the community by an entity entices me for investment.	.883	
66. News/media largely influence my investment decisions.		.802
67. Political instability is a major cause of my investment decision.		.877
15. Absolute awareness in stock markets is important for an investor.		.821
18. Gain realization is an important factor in disposing a stock investment.		.734
19. I have certain skills in picking stocks compared to others.		.843
48. My ability and understanding regarding stock market can help me succeed in the market.		.766
70. Feelings for the products and services of an entity affect my investment options.		.833
87. Statements from government officials regarding the firm urge me to invest.		.775

Table 7
Presentation of observed variables with item statements

Factors	Composition (Observed variables from interview questions)	Factor Loading
Economic Expectation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> The quantity of stock from other investors affects my investment making decisions. 	.838
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> The expected prices and the types of stocks from other investors affect my investment making decisions. 	.894
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> The buying and selling behavior of other investor affects my investment making decisions. 	.867
Herding Effect	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> The analysis of other investors is important in buying and selling equities. 	.729
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> I consider the reactions of other investors in making my investments. 	.770
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> I consider the stock marketability of firm before investing. 	.724
Market Information	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> The highest safety considerations in my stock investments are assured in making investment options. 	.701
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> The future condition in the economy is considered in making investment options 	.804
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> The information from different outlet such as brochures and magazines of financial entities help me in making investment options. 	.796
Third Party Opinion	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Family member's opinions in investment decisions matter in making investment options. 	.737
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> My friend or co-worker recommendations help me in investments. 	.791
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> I like to invest on stocks which are well recommended by family members. 	.812
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Friend recommendations matters on my investment decisions. 	.770
Financial Information	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> History in the market experiences affects my investment decisions. 	.743
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> . Forecasting of share prices and the accounting performance is considered in making investment options. 	.788
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> The recent rate of returns of my investment impacts my investment activities. 	.819
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> I make sure that the rate of return is equal to or higher than the average returns before making investment options. 	.661
Firm Ethics	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Perceived ethics of the firm affects my decision to invest. 	.872

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Involvement in the enhancement of the community by an entity entices me for investment. 	.883
News and Government Influence	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • News/media largely influence my investment decisions. 	.802
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Political instability is a major cause of my investment decision. 	.877
Overconfidence	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Absolute awareness in stock markets is important for an investor. 	.821
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • I like to sell the stock to realize the gains now. 	.734
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • I have certain skills in picking stocks compared to others. 	.843
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • My ability and understanding regarding stock market can help me succeed in the market. 	.766
Firm Image	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Feelings for the products and services of an entity affect my investment options. 	.833
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Statements from government officials regarding the firm urge me to invest. 	.775

Portrayed in Figure 1 is the final framework of the factors that influences the investment decision practices of certified public accountants in Davao del Norte. These factors are comprised of economic expectation, herding effect, market information, third-party opinion, financial information, firm ethics, news and media influence, over-confidence and firm image.

Figure 1. Final Framework Showing the Factors of Investment Decision Practices among Certified Public Accountants in Davao Del Norte

IV. CONCLUSION AND DISCUSSION

From the 100 items that were subjected to exploratory factor analysis, nine factors were discovered. The nine components or dimensions of service quality of multi investment making decision practices of certified public accountants are *Economic Expectation*, *Herding Effect*, *Market Information*, *Third Party Opinion*, *Financial Information*, *News and Government Influence*, *Firm Perception*, *Over-confidence* and *Firm Image*.

Economic Expectation is the first factor that characterizes the investment decision practices of CPAs. In economics, assumptions refer to predictions or opinions held by decision-makers about future costs, revenues, wages, taxes, or other significant variables. It frequently has a huge effect on current decisions taken by businesses and households, as well as current prices and the overall level of economic activity. The first component generated affirms with the study of Gill et al. (2018), which averred that Forecasted expectations about the economy about what type of results an individual will produce in the coming period, i.e., next month, next year, or other length, shape investment decisions. Expectations regarding wages, production, company growth, balance of trade, and inflation rate are examples of these expectations. These projections are for both the company's projected profits and the economy as a whole (Kanojia Singh and Goswami, 2018; Sultana and Pardhasadhi, 2012).

The second factor is the Herding Effect since its attributes speak of behavior that perceives other investors' analysis as influential in buying and selling equities, consider other investors' reactions before investing, and consider the firm's stock marketability before investing. The herding effect refers to investors' proclivity to imitate the behavior of others. Some research considers this effect to be an intraday phenomenon, which makes intuitive sense. When investors have little time to make investment decisions, they are more likely to mimic others rather than evaluate the information they get (Keswani, Dhingra and Wadhwa, 2019).

It is corroborated by Singh and Kumar's (2017) studies purporting that Investors are susceptible to mimicking the behavior of their peers. This investor crowd activity is a major contributor to speculative bubbles, since it means that investors make similar trading decisions, causing stock prices to diverge from their fundamental value. Since individual stocks' weak ability to mimic individuals' habits that have a remarkable ability to develop their investment decision, it can significantly contribute to the analysis and performance assessment. Furthermore, the finding of Islamoglu et al. (2015) avers that Individual investors, unlike institutional investors, herded during market downturns and, to a lesser degree, during market upturns. Individual investment decisions were prone to sentiment during market stress, but they mostly trusted their beliefs and information when stock prices rose, implying that individual investment decisions were prone to sentiment during market stress. Lastly, according to Phuoc and Thi (2011), herding is usually carefully considered by practitioners because investors rely on collective information more than private information, which can lead to a price deviation of securities from their fundamental value. As a result, many current investment opportunities may be harmed. Different academic researchers are also interested in herding; its effects on stock price fluctuation can affect risk and return models, influencing asset pricing theories' perspectives.

Market Information is the third factor in investment decision-making practices, and it includes items such as ensuring that stock investments are safe, considering future economic conditions of the country before making investment decisions, and searching for information from magazines and financial institution brochures to aid in financial decision-making. Market information refers to information that is current and up-to-date, allowing farmers to negotiate with marketers and secondary value-chain participants from a position of greater strength. Farmers can negotiate with traders from a position of strength when they have up-to-date, or current, market information. It also helps with the spatial distribution of products from rural to urban areas, as well as between urban markets, by sending clear price signals from urban consumers to rural producers about the quantities and varieties needed (Food and Agriculture Organization [FAO], 2018).

This factor is comparable to Sarwar and Afaf (2016) findings that mentioned in their research that For investors, data on stock market fluctuations, press coverage, Internet information, and recent price movements are critical. It has also been stated that price volatility and manipulation are the primary sources of concern for retail investors. It has been stressed in the study of Gill et al., (2018) that In order to reduce the risk associated with investment decisions, information plays a critical role. Investors who are better informed can make better decisions about where to look for more market information to reduce the risk of their investment decisions. Because it allows them to reduce uncertainty in investing, well-informed investors can manage risk more effectively.

Third-Party Opinion is the fourth factor in investment decision-making behavior. Its characteristics indicate that when making investment decisions, it considers the opinions of friends, coworkers, or family members. A third party is an entity or person who is involved in a transaction but is not one of the principals and thus has a minor or no interest in the outcome. Finding "Third-Party Opinion" as the fourth dimension of investment making decision practices of certified public accountants in Davao del Norte is in conformance to the studies of Jagongo and Mutswenje, (2014) who postulated that an investor who owns a stock has the option to respond to an analyst's recommendation. It is comparable to Kim et al. (2017) findings, which consider for many economic activities, the family serves as the decision-making unit. Individuals interact with and are influenced by family members, and family influences money beliefs, attitudes, management styles, and behaviors. To put it another way, advocate recommendations are extremely important in investment decisions. (Sarabidya and Saha, 2018). However, in the study conducted by Obamuyi (2013), third-party opinion or opinions of family members is considered the least influencing factors of investment making decisions.

The fifth factor refers to behavior that bases future investments on previous market experiences and forecasts future stock price changes based on the entity's recent stock prices and financial information. This factor is named Financial Information. Zayol, Agaregh, and Eje, (2017) viewed Financial information as the monetary value of the outcomes of company activities It claims that financial information's perceived relevance is to provide reliable information about a

business investment opportunity's true and actual financial position, performance (profitability), and changes in financial position. It may help a wide variety of people make informed or reasonable investment decisions, including potential investors, managers, executives, financial firms, financial analysts, government, regulatory agencies, the media, vendors, and the general public. This factor also affirms the study of Gill et al., (2018), which states that when making investment decisions, rational investors, especially institutional investors, must consider both operational and financial aspects as well as stock growth prospects. Investors may obtain some information by performing a digital or advice-seeking search in general. This findings are also parallel to Obaidat (2016) pronouncement, stating that Stock pricing, failure prediction, performance assessment, optimal contracting, and other decision-making contexts all benefit from accounting data.

Furthermore, reiterated in the study of Zayol et al. (2017) that Financial statement review determines the firm's fiscal strength and weakness when making investment decisions. It will show the red flags of an investment opportunity, as well as the company's strength and the future benefit from investing in it. Finally, the disclosure of appropriate accounting information protects investors, thus increasing consumer trust in the market, which is important for the market to work efficiently Farj et al. (2016).

The sixth factor of investment decision practices is Firm Ethics. This item perceives the firm's ethics and its involvement in solving community problems are essential in deciding on an investment. Firm ethics applies to a company's acceptable policies and procedures in relation to potentially contentious topics such as corporate governance, insider trading, bribery, sexism, corporate social responsibility, and fiduciary duties (Investopedia, 2020)

This factor matches the idea of Chaubey et al. (2016), which mentions a major rise in demand from certain investors who want their investments to be profitable as well as meet certain non-financial requirements. To put it another way, investors are motivated by a sense of moral responsibility to strike a balance between the acquisition of wealth and ethical or societal issues. However, ethical investment decisions are subject to a variety of biases, human decisions are subject to a variety of cognitive illusions, psychological factors affect investor decisions, and the fear of losing money induces the psychological effect (Kannadhasan, 2008). Also, Investors may be enticed by jargon from time to time, but it has been confirmed that the return on an investment, including the conventional investment listed previously, is still their primary concern (Chaubey et al., 2016).

The seventh factor of investment making decision behavior is News and Government Influence. Its attributes speak of a behavior that perceives news, media, and political instability largely influence making investment decisions. During a boom, stock prices respond more quickly to bad news than during a recession. Investors overreact to bad news during economic booms and under-react to bad news during economic depressions, according to an analysis of their responses to both positive and negative news during booms and recessions. It has been found that when news is released, the shares have a lower negative stock return than when news is not announced. And piece of news, whether it's market, company-specific, corporate, political, or economic news, creates a ripple in the investor's mind as he tries to forecast the unpredictable future, and he makes decisions under time and uncertainty constraints (Shantha and Vedantam, 2019; Cox, Dayanandan and Donker, 2016).

This factor is also congruent to the study conducted by Sarbabidya and Saha (2018), which connotes that statements of politicians affect investment decisions. Also, Bialowolski and Weziak-Bialowolska (2013) postulated that The most important and generally understood external factors affecting, and thus likely to hinder, investment decisions are those relating to a country's macroeconomic prospects and monetary policy. To put it another way, obstacles to investment can be influenced by the state of existing regulations in a country that prioritizes environmental protection. The most significant of these is tax policy, which has a direct effect on the rate of return on investment (Ozorio et al., 2013).

The eighth factor of investment making decision behavior is Overconfidence. These attributes speak of behavior that considers confidence and complete knowledge of stock markets in investment decisions. It also means that you can sell the stock right away in order to cash in on your profits. Overconfidence bias is characterized as a systematic overestimation of one's judgment accuracy and information precision (Dittrich et al., 2014). Overconfidence implies that investors are not as smart as they think they seem to be. Overconfidence Bias is putting excessive confidence in an individuals' insight. When it occurs due to the uncertainty, and then these both create mis-reactions. According to psychologists, overconfidence helps the individual exaggerate his abilities and minimize the fear of loss. (Iram et al., 2020)

This factor is a corollary to the study of Gill et, al (2018). Investors who are overconfident claim that other people's investment decisions are affected by their thoughts, perceptions, feelings, and moods. They do, however, make their own choices based on well-considered and logical thoughts. However, another group of critics argues that these individuals trade excessively, noting that they not only trade more but also have a higher risk exposure.

Lastly, the ninth factor of investment making decision behavior is Firm Image. These characteristics characterize investment activity that is influenced by government officials' comments about making investments and is focused on feelings about a company's goods and services. It is backed up by the studies of Sultana and Pardhasaradhi (2012) and Jagongo and Mutswenje (2014). The findings of these studies suggest that annual reports are helpful to corporate shareholders. In addition, the majority of shareholders polled want the company to report on corporate ethics, employee relations, and community engagement. As a consequence, if a company's reputation is positive, it draws more investment.

As a conclusion, the generation of the investment decision-making factors of certified public accountants disproves the Traditional Finance Theory by Markowitz in 1952 and named by Eugene Fama in 1970. That theory portrays investors to be entirely rational while making their investment decisions. Although there are factors extracted that support rationality in making investment decisions like Economic Expectation and Financial Information, among others. Nevertheless, there were also factors extracting showing the irrational practices of CPA's in making investment decisions adhering to the theory of Behavioral Finance contributed by Kahneman and Tversky in 1979, which opines investors' irrational behavior making investment decisions. Investors' practices are rife with biases, and these biases play a major role in making investment decisions.

Based on the results of the study, the researcher proposed the following recommendations; the investors may consider these biases as a risk factor associated with their investment decision. They must prepare a checklist of these factors before making any decision as informed investors. The above study can be further extended to other parts of the regions and may include other consideration biases. The results of the report, as well as the derived model, may be used by the Philippine Institute of Certified Public Accountants in Davao del Norte to enhance its investment decision-making actions. The derived investment making decision behavior model will likewise be suggested as a basis for them in imposing investment decisions for their benefit. Furthermore, the generated factors may be focused on by the accounting sectors in Commerce and Industry, Public, Government, and Academe. Future researchers should conduct more studies on the factors that affect investment decision-making activities in a wider scope or using a different statistical approach, and qualitative interpretation of the study's results is recommended to corroborate the findings.

REFERENCES

- [1] S. Gill., M.K. Khurshid, S. Mahmood & A. Ali, 'Factors Effecting Investment Decision Making Behavior: The Mediating Role of Information Searches', *European Online Journal of Natural and Social Sciences*, 7(4), 2018, 758-767.
- [2] T.N. Mahalakshmi & N. Anuradha, Factors affecting Investment Decision making & Investment Performance among Individual Investors in India. *International Journal of Pure and Applied Mathematics*. 118(18), 2018, 1167-1177.
- [3] A. Farooq, M.A Afzal, N. Sohail & M. Sajid, Factors Affecting Investment Decision Making: Evidence from Equity Fund Managers and Individual Investors in Pakistan. 2015, 62-69
- [4] S.A Qureshi, K. Rehman & A.I Hunjra, 'Factors Affecting Investment Decision Making of Equity Fund Managers', *Wulfenia Journal*, 19(10), 2012, 280-291.
- [5] Islamoglu, Apan & Ayvali, Determination of Factors Affecting Individual Investor Behaviours: A Study on Bankers. *International Journal of Economics and Financial Issues*. 5(2), 2015, 531-543.
- [6] J. Gliem, Calculating, interpreting, and reporting Cronbach's alpha reliability coefficient for likert-type scales, *American Educational Journal*, 2(3), 2003,45-56.
- [7] J.F Hair, M. Sarstedt, L. Hopkins & Kuppelwisser, 'A Primer on Partial Least Squares Structural Equation Modeling (PLS-SEM), (2nd Edition), Sage Publication Inc. 2016, 384.
- [8] H.F. Kaiser, & J. Rice, Little Jiffy, Mark IV. *Educational and Psychological Measurement*, 34(1), 1974, 111-117.
- [9] J.S. Armstrong, & P. Soelberg, 'On the interpretation of factor analysis. *Psychological Bulletin*', 70(5), 1968, 361.
- [10] S. Kanojia, D. Singh & A. Goswami, 'An Empirical Analysis Of The Factors Influencing Individual Investors In The Indian Stock Market', *Journal of Business and Management*, 20(3), 2018, 30-37.

- [11] S. Keswani, V. Dhingra & A. Wadhwa, 'Impact of Behavioral Factors In Making Investment Decisions and Performance: Study on Investors of National Stock Exchange', *International Journal of Economics and Finance*, 11(8), 2019, 80-90.
- [12] A. Singh & Kumar, Review on behavioural factors affecting investment decisions. *Research Journal of Management*, 6(5), 2017, 50-53
- [13] L. Phouc & T. Rhi, Behavioral factors influencing Individual investors' decision-making and performance: A survey at the Ho Chi Minh Stock Exchange. *Cogent Business & Management*. (3), 2016, 103.
- [14] Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nations (FAO), 2018. The Role of Market Informatio. <http://www.fao.org/3/AB795E/ab795e02.htm>
- [15] A. Sarwar & G. Afaf, 'A Comparison Between Psychological And Economic Factors Affecting Individual Investor's Decision Making Behavior', *Cogent Business and Management*, 3(1), 2016, 1-18.
- [16] A. Jagongo & Mutswenje, A Survey of the Factors Influencing Investment Decisions: The Case of Individual Investors at the NSE. *International Journal of Humanities and Social Science*, 4(4), 2014, 92- 102
- [17] A. Kim, Gutter & Spangler, Review of Family Financial Decision Making: Suggestions for Future Research and Implications for Financial Education. *Journal of Financial Counseling and Planning*. (28), 2017, 253-267.
- [18] S. Sarbabidya & Saha, Factors Affecting Investment Decisions: A Study on Bangladesh Stock Market. *Journal of Accounting, Finance and Economics*. 8(2). 2018, 1-19.
- [19] T.M Obamuyi, Factors influencing investment decisions in capital market: a study of individual investors in Nigeria. *Organizations and Markets in Emerging Economies*, vol. 4, no. 1(7), 2013, 141-161.
- [20] Zayol, Agaregh & Eje, Effect of Financial Information on Investment Decision Making By Shareholders of Banks in Nigeria. *IOSR Journal of Economics and Finance*. (8). 2017, 20-31.
- [21] Farj, Jais & Isa, Importance of Accounting Information to Investors in the Stock Market: A Case Study of Libya. *IOSR Journal of Economics and Finance*, 7(1), 2016, 70-79.
- [22] Chaubey, Dev & Patra, A study on the Ethical Considerations in Investors' Investment Decisions. *Splint International Journal of Professionals*. Volume 3(5). 2016, 1-17.
- [23] Kannadhasan, "Role of behavioural finance in investment decisions". *The Journal of Investing*.14. 2008, 66-78.
- [24] G. B Shantha & S.R Vedantam, 'Influence of News on Rational Decision Making by Financial Market Investors', *Investment Management and Financial Innovations*, 16(3), 2019, 142-156.
- [25] R.A.K Cox , A. Dayanandan & H. Donker, 'The Ricochet Effect of Bad News', *The International Journal of Accounting*, 51(3),2016, 385-401.
- [26] Bialowolski & Weziak-Bialowolska, External Factors Affecting Investment Decisions of Companies. *Economic Discussion Paper*. 20(13), 2013, 44.
- [27] L.D.M. Ozorio, C.D.L Bastian-Pinto, T.K.N Baidya & L.E.T Brandao, 'Investment Decision in Integrated Steel Plants Under Uncertainty', *International Review of Financial Analysis*, (27) 2013,, 55-64.
- [28] Dittrich, Guth & Maciejovsky, Overconfidence in Investment Decisions- An Experimental Approach. *European Journal of Finance*, 2010, 1-24.
- [29] T. Iram ,A.R Bilal & K.B Dost, 'Behavioral Factors Affecting the Investment Decision of an Individual: A systematic Review', *Journal of Xidian University*, 14(8),2020, 774-804.
- [30] S. Sultana & S. Pardhasaradhi, An empirical analysis of factors influencing 57ehavi individual equity investors' decision making and behavior. *European Journal of Business and Management*, 4(18), 2012, 50-61.
- [31] H.M Markowitz, Portfolio Selection. *Journal of Finance*, 7, 1952, 77-91.
- [32] E Fama, Efficient Capital Markets: A Review of Theory and Empirical Work" *Journal of Finance*, *American Finance Association*, vol. 25(2),1970, 383-417.